

APPLICATION OF FOAM CORE TO CFRP SANDWICH MIRRORS FOR SPACE TELESCOPES

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1 Introduction

Space telescopes achieve high-accuracy observation regardless of influence of the atmosphere, due to observe outside the earth's atmosphere. In the satellite structures, primary mirrors of the space telescopes are the heaviest part. However, because of severe weight restriction when launching into spaces, lighter mirrors are required. On the other hand, larger mirrors are also required to achieve higher performance. Hence, materials with lightweight, high stiffness and high stable are suitable for mirror material. Though glass or SiC were conventionally used for mirrors, these materials are too heavy to achieve areal density less than 5kg/m². So, using CFRP (carbon fiber reinforced plastic) sandwich panels has been focused on because of its light weight, high rigidity, and extreme low thermal expansion. However, according to previous studies, CFRP sandwich mirrors could not achieve surface accuracy less than $\lambda/20$ (λ : observation wavelength) due to following issues.

- 1) Increment of surface roughness due to carbon fiber print-through [1].
- 2) Hygroscopic deformation of CFRP skin due to fiber misalignment and inhomogeneous fiber volume fraction [2].
- 3) Occurrence of honeycomb core dimples on the skin at extreme low temperature [3].

1) is reduced by "replica method [4]" (coating of epoxy resin which transferred the surface shape of optical-flat glass), and 2) can be reduced by using of cyanate ester resin which is low moisture absorption. However, no effective solutions for 3) have not been reported yet. Though to increase the CFRP skin thickness is one of the solutions, it also increases the weight of the mirrors. On the basis of these backgrounds, we focused on using foam cores to

achieve dimple-less mirrors. According to previous study, it is revealed that moisture absorption is the largest cause of deformation in CFRP mirrors [5]. Therefore, in this study, we measured the surface shape of foam core CFRP mirrors at immediately after fabrication and after holding in hot and high-humidity environment. In addition, we performed FEM (finite element method) analyses to obtain the optimum foam core properties. On the basis of the results, we aimed to suggest a mirror structure with dimple-less, low-areal density, and high-surface precision.

2 Measurement of deformation of foam core mirrors

2.1 Samples and test procedure

Specimens are composed of CFRP skins, adhesive films, and core materials. The skins were 8 ply quasi-isotropic CFRP ([0/±45/90]s), reinforced by pitch-based carbon fiber (K1352U, Mitsubishi plastics Co. Ltd.). For the matrix, cyanate ester (EX-1515, TenCate) was used. The adhesives were epoxy resin films with thickness of 60 μm. The cores were three kinds of polymethacrylimide closed-cell foam ROHACELL (51WF, 51RIST, and 51RIMA). The ROHACELLS possess excellent mechanical properties and low density (0.052 g/cm³). Table 1 shows average cell size of each core. Three kinds of ROHACELLS have the same mechanical properties (by catalog) and have different cell size. In addition, a conventional aluminum honeycomb was also used for comparison. To reduce the carbon fiber print-through on the mirror samples, epoxy resin which transferred the surface shape of optical-flat glass (Replica) were coated. The CFRP skin was 150 mm×150 mm×1 mm and core height was 10 mm. Thickness of replica coating is approximately 30 μm. The areal density of all the prepared mirror samples

was approximately 3.3 kg/m^2 . Figure 1 shows pictures of all the specimens. Surface shape of the mirrors immediately after fabrication was measured by He-Ne laser interferometer (Zygo, GPI-XP, Fig.2). Afterwards, the mirrors were kept in a chamber (as-one, THR040) with constant temperature and humidity at $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 90 \%RH . Surface shapes of the mirrors at after 12 days, 2 months and after re-dried in a 100°C vacuum chamber were measured by a white light interferometer (Zygo, NewView7300, Fig.3).

Table 1 Average cell size of each core in this study.

	ROHAC ELL 51WF	ROHAC ELL 51RIST	ROHAC ELL 51RIMA	Al honeycomb(for comparison)
Cell size, mm	0.657	0.215	0.0346	6.4

Fig.1 CFRP mirror samples with cores of (a) ROHACELL 51WF, (b) ROHACELL 51RIST, (c) ROHACELL 51RIMA and (d) Aluminum honeycomb.

Fig.2 He-Ne laser interferometer (Zygo, GPI-XP).

Fig.3 White light interferometer (Zygo, NewView7300).

2.1 Results and discussion

Figure 4 represents the surface roughness shape of the mirrors at each condition. The surface roughness was measured by applying a FFT filter (cut-off wavelength was $15000 \mu\text{m}$) to eliminate the large out-of-plane deformation. From Fig.4, it is found that obvious dimples appear on honeycomb core mirrors at immediately after fabrication, and that the roughness attributed by the dimples still remained even at re-dry condition. The dimples observed at immediately after fabrication should be caused by

CTE (coefficient of thermal expansion) mismatch between honeycomb and CFRP. On the other hand, the dimples observed after moisture absorption should be caused by creep deformation. On the ROHACELL core mirrors, linear grooves in the direction of 0, ± 45 , 90° were observed at immediately after fabrication. The direction and the distance between grooves show that these grooves are due to fiber print-through. Though these grooves disappeared due to moisture absorption, some embosses appeared after moisture absorption due to local moisture content.

Figure 5 represents the out-of-plane deformation shape of the mirrors at each condition. This figure shows that, though large out-of-plane deformation occurred for ROHACELL core mirrors, it was very small for honeycomb core mirror. In addition, residual deformations are appeared at re-dry condition for the mirrors with ROHACELL core of 51WF and 51RIST. Those deformations were slightly convex. These results imply that low-modulus foam core can't resist the deformation due to Replica coating on one side and misalignment. In addition, moisture expansion of foam core and collapse of the cells due to moisture absorption are also possible reasons for the deformation of the ROHACELL core mirrors. The result for the sample with the core of 51RIMA shown different deformation with other two samples. One of the possible reasons for this is that a debonding between the skin and the core was occurred due to moisture

absorption.

Figure 6 represents the obtained surface roughness (root mean square: RMS values) as a function of cell size of the cores. It is demonstrated that ROHACELL core mirrors could achieve lower roughness than honeycomb core mirrors in all conditions, and that residual deformation is appeared after re-drying.

Figure 7 represents the obtained surface accuracy (RMS values) as a function of cell size of the cores. It is seen from Fig.7 that, though large out-of-plane deformation occurred in ROHACELL core mirrors, it was very small in the honeycomb core mirrors, and that residual deformation is appeared after re-drying. Only $0.1 \mu\text{m}$ RMS deformation appeared in honeycomb core mirrors. On the other hand, the deformation for the ROHACELL core mirrors was $0.7\sim 7 \mu\text{m}$ RMS. The maximum surface accuracy value for RIST core mirrors is $1.9 \mu\text{m}$ RMS. Considering the needs of less than $\lambda/20$ deformation, this result presents that ROHACELL core mirror with $\phi 70$ mm area has a potential to be used for detecting infrared ray with wavelength of longer than $38 \mu\text{m}$. However, we aims to manufacture primary mirrors with $\phi 2$ m available for detecting near-infrared wavelength in this study. To achieve the aim, mirrors with further smaller deformation is required.

Fig.4 Experimentally obtained surface roughness on for each samples (observed area was 15 mm in diameter.).

Fig.5 Experimentally obtained out-of plane deformation for each samples (observed area was 70 mm in diameter.)

Fig.6 RMS values of the surface roughness for each sample.

Fig.7 RMS values of the surface accuracy for each sample.

3 FEM analyses of deformation of foam core mirrors

3.1 Analysis condition

The experimental results shown that large out-of-

plane deformation appeared on foam core mirrors by exposing in hot and high-humidity environment. In order to reveal the mechanism of the large deformation, analyses based on FEM were performed. In the analyses, ANSYS ver.13.0 (ANSYS, Inc.) was used. Figure 8 schematically illustrates an analytical model of the foam core CFRP mirror, and Fig.9 represents a meshed model. Size of the model was 150×150 mm. The CFRP skins had quasi-isotropic fiber orientation of $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ and laminate thickness was 1 mm. The thickness of the foam core was 10 mm, and that of adhesive films was $60 \mu\text{m}$. Replica was coated on one surface with thickness of $30 \mu\text{m}$. In the models, hexahedral elements were used, and in-plane sides of the model were divided into 40×40 elements. In the thickness direction, the replica layer, adhesive layers and CFRP lamina layers had 1 element, and the core had 4 layers. The total elements of the model were 36800. At point A (see Fig.9), displacement of X and Y-direction was fixed, and X, Y, Z-direction at point B and Y-direction at point C were also fixed. These boundary conditions lead to restriction of rigid motion and rotation in all directions, and to permission of only out-of-plane deformations.

In the analyses, maximum moisture content (M_∞) of each material was applied to all nodes in order to evaluate the deformation when the moisture absorption of the samples was saturated. Table 2 represents the material properties of CFRP, replica, adhesive and foam core. For the foam core, 3 different Young's modulus and coefficient of moisture expansion (CME) were used in order to evaluate the effect of core properties. These values assumed the Young's modulus and CME for ROHACELL, Carbon foam and Phenolic resin foam. In addition, analysis using a model with Al honeycomb core was also carried out for comparison. Table 3 represents the material properties of the Al honeycomb core.

Fig.8 Schematic illustration of the analytical model of a CFRP sandwich panel.

Fig.9 The meshed FEM model for analyses.

Table 2 Material properties of CFRP and Epoxy resin.

		E , GPa	G , GPa	ν	CME, $10^{-4}/\%$	M_{∞} , wt%
CFRP (Epoxy/pitchCF)	X	346	$G_{xy}=4.2$	$\nu_{xy}=0.33$	0.21	1.2
	Y	5.3	$G_{yz}=1.89$	$\nu_{yz}=0.4$	40	
	Z	5.3	$G_{xz}=4.2$	$\nu_{xz}=0.33$	67	
Replica, Adhesive (Epoxy resin)		3	-	0.3	67	1.3
Foam core		0.075	-	0.33	0.5	8
		0.5			5	
		2			10	

Table 3 Material properties of core materials

		E , GPa	G , GPa	ν	CME, $10^{-4}/\%$	M_{∞} , wt%
Al Honeycomb	X	2.83×10^{-3}	$G_{xy}=7.85 \times 10^{-4}$	$\nu_{xy}=0.99$	0	0
	Y	2.83×10^{-3}	$G_{yz}=0.39$	$\nu_{yz}=3 \times 10^{-5}$		
	Z	2.8	$G_{xz}=0.39$	$\nu_{xz}=3 \times 10^{-4}$		
ROHACELL 51WF, ROHACELL 51RIST, ROHACELL 51RIMA		0.075	-	0.33	5	8
GRAFOAM FPA-10		0.5	-	0.33	0.5	15

3.2.1 Surface deformation of ROHACELL core mirrors

Figure 10 shows out-of-plane deformation appeared

on the surface of the ROHACELL core mirror without fiber misalignment. In Fig.10, surface depressions were observed along the edge of the model (edge effect), and the edge effect was concentrated at four corners. Figure 11 shows

deformation shape of the ROHACELL core along lines of *A*, *B*, *C* depicted in Fig.10, and along the line *A* on the honeycomb core. From Fig.11, it is revealed that, though the edge effect did not appear on the honeycomb core, it clearly appeared on ROHACELL core. This is because of large shear stress in the skin caused by large hygroscopic expansion of foam. In Fig.11, the deformation is the largest in the diagonal direction. It is expected that the deformation is the most affected by the fiber orientation in the outermost layer. Figure 11 shows convex deformation is observed around the center of the specimen for all cores. However, the convex deformation did not appear when analyses were performed without replica (Fig.12). These results show that the convex deformation is occurred due to replica coating on one surface. To increase core height and to enhance bending stiffness should be an effective way to reducing convex deformation. However, deformation caused by edge effect is larger than the convex deformation by replica. Along the line *B*, the calculated deformation was 8 μmPV . This deformation is too large to ignore for the mirrors in which the deformation is desired to be less than sub-micron scale. Therefore, to decrease the edge effect is required to achieve high-accuracy mirrors.

Fig.10 Analytically calculated surface deformation of a ROHACELL core mirror.

Fig.11 Surface deformation profile of mirrors with Al honeycomb and ROHACELL core.

Fig.12 Deformation profile of ROHACELL core mirror with and without replica.

3.2.2 Comparison with experimental result

In the experiments, the deformations were measured in the range of $\phi 70$ mm around the center of the specimen. To compare the analytical results with the experimental ones, we focused on the area of $\phi 70$

mm in the analytical results. Table 4 shows the analytical and experimental results of surface accuracy in $\phi 70$ mm area. In this table, the values of “experimental result” were determined as difference between the deformation obtained immediately after fabrication and that obtained after absorption for 2 months. In Table 4, experimental results for ROHACELL core (51WF and 51RIST) are larger than that for analytical result, and the experimental results for Honeycomb core is smaller than that for analytical results. One reason for this should be that the matrix resin used in the experiments was different from that assumed in the analyses. Though the material properties of epoxy resin were used as the matrix resin in the analyses, cyanate ester resin was used as matrix resin in the experimental sample. The amount of moisture absorption for the cyanate ester resin is lower than that for the epoxy resin. Therefore, the deformation in the experiments should be smaller than that in the analyses. This is the reason for the difference between the analytical and experimental results for honeycomb sample. However, this is not the reason for the difference appeared in the ROHACELL core samples.

Table 4 RMS values of deformation value in the area of $\phi 70$ mm around the center of the samples (without fiber misalignment)

	ROHACE LL 51WF	ROHACE LL 51RIST	Al honeyco mb
RMS, μm (Experimental result)	0.362 (3.295)	0.362 (0.699)	0.364 (0.063)
PV, μm (Experimental result)	1.247 (14.315)	1.247 (4.176)	1.260 (0.033)

3.2.3 Effect of core properties on fiber misalignment

In the previous section, we did not take into account the influence of fiber misalignment in FEM model. In this section, we investigate the influence of misalignment of the skin on the deformation. The skins have $+5^\circ$ misalignment in outermost layer in this section, and the deformations were calculated with varying the core CME and Young’s modulus (E). Figure 13 represents the surface deformation of the ROHACELL core mirror. The obtained deformation

shows twist shape due to misalignment on the edge effect. Figure 14 represents the deformation shape along arrow line depicted in Fig.13, and Fig.15 focuses on enclosed area in Fig.14. It is found from Fig.14 that larger edge effect appears in the results for larger CME. Figure 15 shows that, though the deformation around the center of the mirrors increases with decreasing E when CME is small, that decreases with decreasing E when CME is large. Table 5 shows the analytical and experimental results of surface accuracy around the center of the sample (the area in $\phi 70$ mm) obtained with $+5^\circ$ misalignment in the outermost layer as well as shown in Table 4. The experimental results for ROHACELL core sample are still larger than the analytical results. Therefore, these results imply that the fiber misalignment in the skin is not a significant factor for the large deformation obtained in the experiments.

Fig.13 Calculated surface deformation of a ROHACELL core mirror with fiber misalignment (CME: $5.0 \times 10^{-4}\%$, Young’s modulus: 0.075GPa).

Fig.14 Analytically obtained deformation profile of each core mirrors.

Fig.15 Surface deformation focused on around the center of the sample (enclosed are presented in Fig.14).

Table 5 RMS values of deformation in the area of $\phi 70$ mm (with misalignment).

	ROHACE LL 51WF	ROHACE LL 51RIST	Honeycomb
RMS, μm (Experimental result)	0.462 (3.295)	0.411 (0.699)	0.411 (0.063)
PV, μm (Experimental result)	2.99 (14.315)	1.74 (4.176)	1.74 (0.033)

3.2.4 Effect of CME and Young's modulus

The PV values of edge part along the line *B* depicted in Fig.10 for various core CME and *E* are shown in Fig.16. In these analyses, the replica layer was not defined in the models to evaluate only the effect of edge effect. Figure 16 presents that the edge height decreases with decreasing CME and *E*. However, when CME is 0.5×10^{-4} /wt%, the edge height is decrease with increasing *E*. This is because the high-modulus core suppress the edge effect between the skin and adhesive. These results suggest that foam core with smaller CME mismatch between the cores and skins and with higher Young's modulus should be effective to achieve the mirrors with smaller deformation.

Figure 17 and Fig.18 show analytical results calculated from models with a carbon foam core. The carbon foams possess lower CME and higher Young's modulus than ROHACELL cores, and in this analyses material properties for GRAFOAM FPA-10 (GrafTech International Ltd.) were defined for the core. The analytical model included the replica layer, and $+5^\circ$ misalignment was defined in the outermost layer of the skin. In those figures, results calculated from the model with the ROHACELL and the Al honeycomb cores were also presented for comparison. As seen in Fig.17, the edge effect is suppressed by using the GRAFOAM. In addition, it is found from Fig.18 that using GRAFOAM is effective for reduction of convex deformation. Though the reduction of deformation obtained using the GRAFOAM is very small in this analysis (within $1 \mu\text{mPV}$), this effect should be magnified if the mirror is large. Therefore, using carbon foam cores is one option to reduce the deformation.

Fig.16 Calculated height of the edges appeared on the foam core CFRP sandwich panel.

Fig.18 The surface deformation of the mirrors with three different cores (focused on the enclosed area depicted in Fig.17).

Fig.17 Comparison of the surface deformation on GRAFOAM, ROHACELL and Al Honeycomb core mirrors.

3.2.7 Double core CFRP sandwich structure

On the basis of the results presented above, the carbon foam cores have potential to be dimple-less mirrors with low out-of-plane deformation. However, the density of the carbon foams are larger than honeycomb (for example, the density of FPA-10: 0.116 g/mm^3 , CFRP honeycomb: 0.03 g/mm^3), and using carbon foam results in high areal density mirror. To decrease the areal density, using “double-core structure” as shown in Fig.19 is a possible way. This structure is consisted of thin foam layers and a thick honeycomb layer. Thin foam layers should achieve dimple-less surface and low out-of-plane deformation without weight gain, and thick honeycomb layer should achieve high-bending stiffness. By using this structure, both low areal density and high-precision mirror should be achieved.

Fig.19 Schematic illustration of double-core CFRP mirrors.

4 Conclusions

The experimental results shown that, though ROHACELL core CFRP sandwich mirrors achieved lower surface roughness (15 nm RMS) than honeycomb core mirrors, larger out-of-plane deformation (0.7~7 μm RMS) was observed.

From the results of FEM analyses, it was revealed that large edge effect was occurred in foam core mirrors. Using foam core with small CME mismatch and high Young's modulus is effective for to reduce the edge effect. These results suggest that using carbon foam is effective to suppress the out-of-plane hygroscopic deformation.

Large out-of-plane deformation occurred in ROHACELL core mirrors may be caused by weak cell structures.

In addition, the double-core structure has potential to be mirrors with low-areal density, dimple-less and low out-of-plane deformation.

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